

SOUND AND MUSIC COMPUTING MASTER

MASTER DISSERTATION

Automatic Classification of Musical Sounds

in the context of Freesound

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Abstract

Freesound.org is a online sound database with over 200.000 sounds now, which everyday serves the purpose of sound designers, composers and creative artists, providing them with Creative Commons license sounds for them to build musical compositions, interactive installations, build applications, movie soundtracks, etc. The need for optimized ways to serve musical content in this platform, as in others, is much needed, in order not to avoid leaving many sounds to be unexplored and never retrieved. What this work proposes is to develop a content based approach to classify sounds into a two level taxonomy. The first level consists of the classes *Speech*, *Sound Effects*, *Soundscape*, *Music* and *Instrument*. The second level, consists of musically meaningful concepts, such as *Chord*, *Single Note*, *Melody*, among others. Two different set of features are evaluated, MFCC and spectral features against low level features, and two different classification schemes too, flat against hierarchical. For classification, K-Nearest Neighbour, Support Vector Machines and Decision Trees classifiers are used. Evidence is shown the MFCCs and spectral features combined with a hierarchical model works the best. The dataset used is also made available.

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“I was born with music inside me. Music was one of my parts. Like my ribs, my kidneys, my liver, my heart. Like my blood. It was a force already within me when I arrived on the scene. It was a necessity for me like food or water.”

Ray Charles

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In this era of big data and a constant overflow of information with the development of information technology, methods for automatic classifying multimedia content, namely sounds, are needed.

This current work will approach the task of sound classification, one of the most typical ones in the MIR¹ field, into a taxonomy of musical categories such as the one presented in Figure 1.1. The first level of the taxonomy has already been used by Font et al. in Font et al. (2014), while the second level is an addition of this work.

Figure 1.1: Taxonomy for this work.

1.1 Motivation

Many different people and institutions, coming from all different kinds of backgrounds, rely on sites such as Freesound² for creating musical compositions, interactive installations, build applications, compose movie soundtracks, just to name a few. As this

¹Music Information Retrieval

²www.freesound.org

time of writing³, there are over 200.000 unique sounds in Freesound. This is of course a very large number and optimized ways to serve this content to users is needed.

The option that this work explores is to develop the knowledge to be able to query such sounds from a musical concept point of view, e.g. *chord*, *chord progression*, *single note*, *drum hit*, etc. It might be the case that the users introduce this knowledge when uploading their sounds to the platform, but many times that is not the case, leaving many sounds to be unexplored and never retrieved.

For these reasons, the motivation that drives this work is then to **potentiate musical creativity**, by providing creative artists with better structured content, which we assume leads to better creative potential.

1.2 Objectives

The objectives of this work were:

- to develop a system capable of automatically predicting a subset of *Freesound* sounds into a predefined hierarchy of useful musical concepts, such as *chords*, *chord progressions*, *single note*, *drum hit*, to name a few;
- compare a context-based approach (Font et al., 2014) with a content-based approach for the first level of the taxonomy;
- evaluate which set of features is best for the particular classification problem;
- to evaluate two different classification scheme approaches: *flat* and *hierarchical*.

1.3 Relevant Contributions

The first and more important contribution of this work is providing with a content-based system capable of classifying into musically meaningful classes with relatively good accuracies ($\simeq 70\%$), as well as into broad sound clip categories with accuracies as high as 83%. Furthermore, it benchmarks two different kind of set of features for accomplishing this task, showing how one consistently outperforms the other one, MFCCs and spectral features compared to low-level features. Secondly, it provides the community with an annotated dataset, freely available⁴. Lastly, it compares a flat to a hierarchical classification scheme, showing that with the hierarchical one better performance is achieved.

1.4 Structure of the Dissertation

This dissertation is structured in 5 chapters that somewhat resemble the chronologically way in which the present work took place. The current chapter, Chapter 1,

³21st August 2014

⁴<http://paginas.fe.up.pt/~ei08067/5ClassDatasetExtended/>

contextualizes the research conducted, its motivations, aims and main contributions to the field. Chapter 2 provides the theoretical background and explanations to many of the concepts that were of fundamental importance to the work developed, as well as a literature review of the audio clip classification topic. Chapter 3 describes the methodology of the work, namely, the process of creating the datasets and classifiers and features chosen. Chapter 4 details the experiments conducted and its results . Finally, Chapter 5 ends with the discussion of the results, conclusions and future work.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

This chapter provides background introduction to the concepts used to conduct this work, as well as the literature review for the sound clip classification task.

To our attention there is no work that uses the exact same taxonomy that we are interested in studying, therefore making an exact direct comparison between works not really feasible. Nevertheless, despite using different classes for classification, these other works are able to provide with the methodology and knowledge that can be used and adapted for the current work.

Lastly, it is provided a description of Freesound, since the classifier developed will be implemented in that context, using some of its sounds as a database. It is highlighted some works that have used this platform for both research and creative applications purposes.

2.1 Groundtruth

One of the crucial steps towards having valid experiments is the use of ground truth datasets. It is strongly encouraged that these datasets be (i) as balanced as possible (similar number of instances per tag), (ii) as complete as possible (describe music excerpts in all possible ways) and (iii) shared among the scientific community (to encourage exhaustive evaluation and comparison among the different algorithms) (Sordo, 2011, p. 3).

In this work's case of classifying into the taxonomy presented in Figure 1.1, the groundtruth for each of the clips will simply be two classes: one of the first level (*Instrument Sample*, *Sound Effect*, *Soundscape*, *Musical Sample*, *Voice*) and another one for the second level, in some of the categories, such as *Note* and *Percussive Hit* for the *Instrument Sample*.

Details on how the groundtruth for this work was devised is explained in Section 3.1.

2.2 Content and Context

In most classification techniques there are two approaches that are commonly distinguished: *content-based* and *context-based*.

A content-based approach basically means that only the content of the audio is taken into account for solving the classification problem. This implies that the features will be extracted directly from the audio signal in order to characterize it. Some example of content based descriptions of an audio file are the MFCCs, spectral centroid, loudness, among many others.

On the other hand, a context-based approach, uses the contextual information of the objects to be classified into account, such as *text comments*, *number of downloads*, *tag cloud*, etc. In other words, it captures aspects of the audio that are beyond the audio signal, describing sounds in cultural and perceptual terms. Most of these information is provided by users of online communities that tag these resources and contribute to the gathering/generation of this knowledge, which, in the case of the tags, is called *folksonomy*. An example diagram is presented in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Schematic example of a folksonomy. Image from Font and Serra (2012).

The current work follows a context-based approach, so, naturally, more emphasis is put on studying works that followed that same one. One of the objectives of this work, as mentioned in Section 1.2, is to study how a content-based approach performs compared to a context-based approach that has already accomplished rather good results - accuracies between 70% and 90%. That work is of Font et al. (2014), which relies on the input of social tags that are provided by the Freesound community of users to perform the classification problem. Font et al. (2014) also presents a novelty of a tag expansion step for when the clips are scarcely tagged, which improves the performance of the overall method in most cases.

2.3 Audio Features

In order to characterize the audio, it is needed to extract some descriptors (audio features) that are then able to train the classifier and consequently produce a classification for unknown samples. There are in fact a large amount of different features

available, with new ones being created specifically for certain applications. Descriptors can be global (mean, variances, etc.) or instantaneous (on a frame by frame basis). Peeters (2004) provides a great and comprehensive review of many of the most used descriptors in MIR research, dividing them, as it is also most commonly seen in literature into different categories: temporal shape and features, spectral shape, harmonic and perceptual.

There has been a lot of research on which descriptors are better to discriminate for different classification problems. Mel Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCCs) however, have been shown in literature to capture rather well timbre information in virtually all speech and audio related tasks. They were introduced by Davis and Mermelstein (1980) in the 1980's, and have been state-of-the-art ever since. Only the first 13 coefficients are most commonly used. It is also common to use the first and second order derivatives of the MFCC, which are called Δ MFCCs (delta) and $\Delta\Delta$ MFCCs (double delta), respectively.

A review of some works follow. As a first example, Casey (2001) use a hierarchical taxonomy, whose first level classes are *Speech*, *Impacts*, *Foley*, *Music* and *Animals*, as can be seen in Figure 2.2a. It makes use of the MPEG-7 general sound recognition tools, which use de-correlated spectral features. In fact, the features used are a low dimension representation of the spectrum itself. With this approach, Casey obtains an overall accuracy for all classes as high as 92.65%.

A slightly different problem is addressed by Herrera et al. (2002) with the automatic classification of drum sounds with the taxonomy in Figure 2.2b. The conclusion taken is that the features selected through automatic selection processes, where mainly spectral features: skewness, kurtosis, centroid and MFCCs.

Livshin et al. (2003) computes as much as 163 descriptors for all sounds in databases, and then apply automatic feature selection to select the best ones. More information is provided in Section 2.4. The taxonomy used, showed in Figure 2.2c is hierarchical of a instrument classification problem.

Burred (2005) uses a taxonomy, Figure 2.2d, that is arguably not that common in literature, since it mixes the automatic genre classification problem along with Speech (Male/Female/With background) and Background identification. For its features it uses a combination of means and standard deviations (and their derivatives) of low-level features, spectral features, MFCCs and some MPEG-7 standard features too. Given the very high number of features, Burred, uses automatic selection algorithms for each class.

Lastly, Roma et al. (2010), who uses the taxonomy in Figure 2.2e, uses MFCCs features as baseline, although still obtaining comparable results to an optimized set of features. This optimized set of features, most of them from the MPEG-7 standard, is automatically selected using a feature selection algorithm, in order to optimize the discrimination between classes. 7 out of the 13 features selected are spectral related and both means and variances are used.

Figure 2.2: Different taxonomies of audio clip classification works.

2.4 Feature Selection and Decomposition

Due to the high number of available descriptors, it is not uncommon to have to make use of techniques to reduce the dimensionality of the feature space, in order to be able to solve the classification problem in a timely way. However, the reasons for choosing these kind of methods is not only computational, but also to find a more representative description of the same feature space. There are two ways to fundamentally approach this problem of over dimensionality : one is manual, where the research/data analyst specifies the rules to for which features should be considered and the other is automatic, algorithmically determining and/or transforming the features to be used.

The most common automatic feature decomposition techniques are: Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Independent Component Analysis (ICA), Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) and Relevant Component Analysis (RCA). It is out of the scope of this work to provide a description for each one of them. In any case, a very brief summary of the process can be described as applying transformations to the input feature vectors in a way that they become more representative of the problem, which ultimately (and hopefully) results in better performance.

An example of use of an automatic way to select features and reduced the number of descriptors used is the *Gradual Descriptor Elimination* (GDE) algorithm used by Livshin et al. (2003). In fact, in this work, Livshin et al., show how for the simpler problem of detecting if an instrument is of class *pizzicato* or *sustained*, reducing the number of descriptors from 162 down to 3 still yields a classification accuracy of 97.43%, compared to 100% when using all of them, as can be seen in Figure 2.3 along with some other results. Peeters and Rodet (2002) also proposes two methods for automatically selecting the more discriminative descriptors based on user-defined taxonomies and databases, namely Discriminant Analysis and Mutual Information.

Figure 2.3: The effect of GDE (Gradual Descriptor Elimination) of Livshin et al. (2003) on both detecting *Families* of instruments (left) and *Instruments* themselves (right). It is evident as many features are not relevant at all, since the same results are achieved with a very smaller number of features too. Image from Livshin et al. (2003).

2.5 Classification

The framework for most classification problems in the music domain (and image and video) are all roughly identical. They begin with a dataset which is usually annotated before hand (supervised learning), either by experts or by a community (social tagging), although it can as well not be annotated (unsupervised learning). This dataset is then divided into training and testing set. The training one is used to extract features and consequently train a classifier through the use of machine learning algorithms. The test one is used to validate the classifier and consequently compute a numeric value of its performance. In this section, a short review of different techniques for different audio clip classification problems will be presented, which later will help to develop and tackle the current problem of this work, as well as some background information on the topic.

To begin with, it is important to bear in mind some of the non-trivial problems that automatic classification of musical sounds poses (Livshin et al., 2003):

- **Accuracy:** Is it possible to distinguish between almost perceptually identical sounds even though they are coming from different sound sources, for example the *Viola* and the *Violin* in certain registers?

- **Taxonomy:** Depending on the classification problem at hand, most probably it will not be easy to say to exact class a sound sample should belong too. Should a two chord progression chord be classified as a *Chord Progression* or as a *Loop* or even both? Should the classes be mutually exclusive all the time?
- **Generality:** Which are the properties of the sound (sound descriptors) that are more important for discriminating between the classes in the taxonomy, despite the sound database used? Will the classifier be able to generalize to another sound database, maybe recorded in a different environment?
- **Validity of the data:** How accurate is the groundtruth exactly? Are there any misclassified examples that are wrongly influencing the results without an awareness of that?

Casey (2001), for example, proposes the use of Hidden Markov Models to model the evolution of the spectrum over time. For that reason, features are computed every frame rather than summarized. This is the kind of classifier that is not commonly used in the typical sound clip classification approach, since most of the times the features used are global, therefore making impossible the use of classifiers such as this.

Herrera et al. (2002) explores the use of three different type of classifiers: instance-based (K^* , K-Nearest Neighbour), statistical based (Canonical discriminant analysis) and tree-based (C4.5 and the PART variant). In this work, very high accuracies are obtained for all three levels of the taxonomy: 99%, 97%, 90%.

Livshin et al. (2003) suggests some improvements that can be done to the typical approach over instrument classification. The taxonomy used is done in three levels as presented in Figure 2.2c. In this work, Livshin et al. (2003) compare the performance of three different classifiers: *Multidimensional Gauss*, *KNN* and *LVQ (Learning Vector Quantization)*. It also introduces some techniques for removing outliers from the database.

Burred (2005) does not provide much exploration of classifying techniques. It states it uses a 3-cluster Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) and it obtains an overall accuracy of $\simeq 60\%$ for all of the 17 classes of the taxonomy.

Bajpai and Yegnanarayana (2008) reports results for a taxonomy of *advertisement*, *cricket*, *cartoon*, *football* and *news* collected from a TV broadcast. The final approach they present combine two classifiers: a HMM with segmental features and a ANNN (Autoassociative Neural Network) to model audio components and a MPL (Multilayer Perceptron) to classify audio. With this approach they achieve a performance of 86.96% of accuracy. Later, using a rank and measurement level they improve its performance to 92.97%.

Finally, Roma et al. (2010) also do not compare different classifying algorithms, using only Support Vector Machines with a C-SVC kernel, performing a grid search to find the values of C and γ .

On another matter, a point important to consider when classifying into a taxonomy, is if that same taxonomy is *flat* or *hierarchical*. Roma et al. (2010) benchmark these two classification schemes, obtaining a slightly higher accuracy for the *flat* scheme (84.56%)

compared to the hierarchical (81.41%). In that same work, Roma et al., also mentions that the kind of errors that occur at the same level are similar in both approaches, although, this is believed to be mostly problem specific dependent.

Babbar et al. (2013) also addresses this issue, mentioning how it seems not to be a systematic position regarding when a *flat* or a *hierarchical* approach is the best for any given problem. That is the motivation of that work that analyze it in a generalized way. Its main conclusion is that top-down hierarchical classifiers are well suited to unbalanced, large-scale taxonomies, whereas flat ones should be preferred for well-balanced taxonomies. Considering this work’s full taxonomy, it is far from being a large-scale taxonomy, and therefore, according to that, a *flat* classification should expectedly work better.

Other example found in literature comparing a flat and hierarchical approaches is of Burred (2005), that for a taxonomy, such as the one in Figure 2.2d, shows an overall accuracy of 58.71% for the hierarchical scheme and 59.76% for the flat one. These are again, very similar values. It also describes how the errors in the hierarchical approach concentrate better on the second level of the taxonomy, which is an advantage considering the particularities of the that work’s taxonomy.

2.6 Evaluation

The performance of a algorithm/process/system is based on the computation of metrics, that is numbers that reflect how “good” they are. In MIR research the metrics reported depend on the particular problem and even approach. In any classification problem, like it is the case of this work, there will always be the variables of *True Positives* (TP), *True Negatives*, (TN), *False Positives* (FP) and *False Negatives* (FN). Based on this four variables, multiple metrics can be calculated: *Precision*, *Recall*, *F-score*, and *Accuracy* being the more common ones. In this work, only accuracy will be used.

Accuracy is the ratio of correctly predicted classes over all possible classes.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN}$$

Additionally, to have a more in depth idea of the specifics of how the classifier is actually performing for each class, it is common to analyze and many times report the confusion matrix. The confusion matrix is simply a dual entry table where the predicted class is mapped to the actual class. Figure 2.4 is an example of a confusion matrix of a sound class classification problem. This way of visualizing the data allows for more information than just the overall performance of the system per class. In particular, it allows to see where the misclassifications are being more frequent, the biggest one, in this case, being *Samples* instances being predicted as *Music* (11.36%).

Figure 2.4: Confusion matrix obtained by Font et al. (2014). Image from Font et al. (2014)

A important point to bear in mind regarding evaluating a classifier, is how to divide the training from the test set:

- **cross-validation:** This consists of dividing the dataset in equal number of parts and iteratively training and testing with each one of them. The most commonly used number of partitions for the dataset used is normally 10, but this depends on the dataset size. It can be said to be the standard evaluation approach and one that most scientific works report.
- **percentage split:** This is quite similar to the cross validation, but instead of specifying in how many partitions that dataset should be divided, it specifies the percentage of the training set and correspondingly of the training set. It is normally used when there is some assumptions a priori of the dataset and/or classification problem itself.
- **leave-one-out:** it is a very special case of the cross-validation approach, where the classifier is trained with all the instances of the dataset except one, that is then used to test the classifier. This is done iteratively for all instances of the dataset and the results are averaged to report the final performance metric results.

2.7 Freesound

Freesound is an online collaborative sound database where users share their own recorded sound clips under Creative Commons licenses. It is was started in 2005 by the Music Technology Group (MTG) of the Univeristat Pompeu Fabra, which still maintains it. Its aim were/are mainly two: (i) to provide sound researchers with a large collection of royalty-free sounds to test their algorithms, since finding such collections are not generally easy; (ii) to serve the artistic community (composers, musicians, sound

designers, etc.) with easy to use sounds that they could use for artistic/creative purposes. For more information about Freesound, namely implementation details, please refer to Akkermans et al. (2011) and Font et al. (2013a). Also, the interface for a sound page in `Freesound.org` can be seen in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Interface for a sound page in `Freesound.org`. Tags for the sound highlighted in red.

As moment of writing, Freesound contains over 200,000 audio clips and more than 3 million users. Its folksonomy has been object of analysis by Font and Serra (2012), who give insight in many of the intrinsic way of how Freesound users use and tag in this platform. Its tagging system is a *collaborative tagging* type, where users associate different labels (tags) with sound clips, with no restriction whatsoever, apart from the fact that, since September 2011, a minimum of three different tags is necessary to describe each item. The same work also describes how Freesound’s folksonomy, as most folksonomies, is noisy, suffering from problems such as synonymy, polysemy and other kinds of inconsistencies in general. This is one of the motivations of this work, by trying to come up with methods to address this issue and ultimately provide better structured content.

A tag recommendation system was recently implemented in Freesound and is described in Font et al. (2013b), that relies on co-tag occurrence, which is to say, if a sound clip A has the tags X , Y and Z and a user is describing a newly uploaded sound to Freesound and explicitly says that he has tags X and Y , then most probably is going to have tag Z as well.

2.7.1 Freesound in Research

Freesound has been used in a diversity of research activities and fields. An example is Font (2010) master thesis. In this work, Font builds and evaluates a visualization interface for querying the large sound database of sound according to four perceptually meaningful properties of the sound, namely: *temporal envelope*, *timbre*, *tonal information*

and *pitch*. A screenshot of the interface can be seen in Figure 2.6.

Another example is of Roma et al. (2012), which tries to understand the creativity dynamics of audio clip sharing websites, namely Freesound. For this, Roma et al. derives multiple small world networks from website usage metrics (number of downloads per audio file, number of comments, forum usage, etc.). From these small world networks they conduct an empirical study that gives some insight on how to maximize the active community and ultimately creativity.

Lastly, Stowell and Plumbly (2014) used Freesound to build an open dataset, *freefield1010* of 7690 sound clips for the tag *field-recording*, while providing also a simple example of classification using such dataset.

These are only of the many examples where Freesound has been used for research purposes, because there is a lot more of other works using it too.

Figure 2.6: Querying interface for Freesound by Font (2010). Image from (Font, 2010, p. 32).

2.7.2 Freesound in Creative Applications

Freesound has also been used in various creative applications. The Freesound Radio project¹ (Roma et al., 2009) is one of those examples applied to musical creativity. As can be seen in Figure 2.7, this project allows to generate musical ideas/pieces by connecting sound clips in Freesound in a graph manner, with each node corresponding to a clip. Overall, this allows for a quick experimentation of combination of sounds, which is known to be the process many artists take for their compositions.

Eigenfeldt and Pasquier (2011) use the large database of soundscape recordings from Freesound in order to create generative music soundscape compositions. They use an approach of implicit knowledge through the use of agents that analyze the spectral content of the selected samples in order to avoid masking each other. Additionally, they use not only content-based similarity, but also tags to achieve the final compositions.

¹<http://radio.freesound.org>

One of the most recent published works using Freesound in a creative context is of Merz (2013), which uses it to build algorithmic compositions. For this, he creates a graph of similar sounds both perceptually (using the Freesound API²) and lexically (using Wordnik³). Then, he uses a combination of manual editing and multiple automatic algorithms to transverse these graphs and consequently generate music. His compositions are accessible online⁴.

Figure 2.7: Freesound Radio interface. Image from Roma et al. (2009).

Again, there are just a few selected examples of works using Freesound in a creative context, although much more could have been referenced.

²www.freesound.org/docs/api/

³www.wordnik.com

⁴<https://soundcloud.com/evanxmerz>

Chapter 3

Methodology

In this chapter, it will be presented the specific methodology that this work followed. It starts by describing the process that consisted of devising the dataset for the experiments. Then, it outlines the audio features that were chosen and why. Finally, it ends with a description of the both the classifiers and evaluation methodology used.

3.1 Dataset

The starting point for the dataset used in this work is the same used in Font et al. (2014). However, that work considers only what will be referred as the *first level* taxonomy, namely: *Instrument Sample*, *Sound Effect*, *Soundscape*, *Musical Sample* and *Voice*. Therefore, it was necessary to annotate the dataset for the *second level* taxonomy as depicted in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Taxonomy for this work.

Despite most of the concepts of the taxonomy being in general self-explanatory, it is necessary to provide a proper definition, even more because a few might raise some misunderstandings. The concepts of the *first level* taxonomy were already described in the previous work mentioned and their definitions are quoted here for easier reference. A definition for the *second level* taxonomy classes follows too.

Instrument Sample

“This category represents all sorts of instrument samples, including single notes, chords and percussive hits. Typical examples of this category include single notes of a piano recorded one by one and uploaded as different audio clips, or samples from a complete drum set.”

Note

This category is rather straight-forward, consisting of single notes of instruments, which include piano, saxophone, synthesizers and even some custom made instruments from Freesound users, among others.

Percussive Hit

This category consists mainly of drum samples: toms, snares, hi-hats, cymbals and kicks.

Sound Effect

“Here we include all kinds of what is generally known as sound effects, including foley, footsteps, opening and closing doors, alarm sounds, cars passing by, animals, and all kinds of noises or artificially created glitches. In general these tend to be short clips”

Soundscape

“This category includes generally longer recordings resulting of the addition of multiple sounds that, in isolation, would be classified under “Sound Effects”. Examples would be environmental recordings, street ambiances or artificially constructed complex soundscapes.”

Musical Sample

“Here we include more complex musical fragments such as melodies, chord progressions, and drum loops. In the same way as “Soundscape” sounds can be understood as the addition of multiple “Sound Effect”, audio clips under “Music” category can be conceived as combinations of “Instrument Samples”.”

Chord

In this category, most of the samples consists of chords played simultaneously, although some quick arpeggios where the previous notes are left to ring were also consider. The reason for this is to try and mimic how a trained (and even a not so well trained) musician would name the sounds. These include mostly a lot of guitar sounds (clean, jazz, distortion) and piano (processed and non-processed).

Chord Progression

This category consists of sounds that could be seen, musically, as a sequential combination of the previous category. Once again, it was favored sounds where the chords happened simultaneously although not exclusively. Additionally, it implies that there is no (significant) percussive component to the sound.

Loop

This category implies that there is a steady tempo in the sound and that it could be looped. In addition, it implies that there is both a harmonic and percussive component to the sound.

Melody

Just like it was mentioned how the “Chord Progression” could be seen as the set of samples that could result from the sequential combination of sounds from the “Chord” category, the same goes for this category and the “Note” category.

Rhythmic Pattern

This category consists mainly of drum loops, although it also includes many rhythmic and percussive patterns that might not have a clearly established tempo and played by other percussive instruments.

Voice

“The last category includes all sorts of speech-related audio clips such as text reading, single words or recordings of text-to-speech processors.”

The initial idea was to use the exact same sounds by Font et al. (2014), while adding another layer of classification to the *Musical* and *Sample* classes. However, quickly enough, it was clear that was not going to be possible. The reason for this was that for some sounds it was impossible to categorize them into any of the categories. This is not totally unexpected, since the taxonomy used, although broad, does not cover all possible cases, as such is virtually impossible. In order to circumvent this problem, it was then inevitably necessary to find sounds outside the dataset from Font et al. (2014), so that to reduce ambiguity to a minimum. This process of finding new sounds and annotating

them for the second level of the taxonomy was done manually, using, again, Freesound as the sound file resource.

In artist music recognition, another typical task of the MIR field, the *album effect*¹ has been known to happen (Whitman et al., 2001). In the case of user contributed content, as it is the case of sites as Freesound, it makes sense to question if the equivalent, the *user effect*, will happen. Font et al. (2014) addressed this question, having not found influence in their results. For this reason, not a systematic emphasis was put on this aspect when devising the dataset.

The distribution for each class of the dataset is presented in Table 3.1.

Class	# Sounds
Instrument Sample	1000
> <i>Note</i>	500
> <i>Percussive Hit</i>	500
Sound Effect	1000
Soundscape	1000
Musical Example	1000
> <i>Chord</i>	200
> <i>Chord Progression</i>	200
> <i>Loop</i>	200
> <i>Melody</i>	200
> <i>Rhythmic Pattern</i>	200
Voice	1000
Total	5000

Table 3.1: Distribution of the classes in the dataset.

3.2 Features

After the literature review done for the audio features used in similar problems, in Section 2.3, it was chosen to adopt two different set of features, as seen in Table 3.2. The first one consists of low-level features, mostly spectral ones, which are listed at Appendix A.2. The other one consists of exclusively MFCCs and spectral features. For a full list, please refer to Appendix A.1. Both of the sets include means and variances.

¹Phenomenon that happens when better classification results are achieved, when songs from the same album are used both in the training and evaluation data sets.

Feature set	#Descriptors
Low-level	58
MFCC+SF	72

Table 3.2: Set of features used in this work.

Additionally, once again, in line with the literature review that was done, feature decomposition techniques like *PCA*, *ICA* and *LDA* are used, since they have been shown to be of big importance in similar problems. Table 3.3 shows the methods and corresponding parameters used in Section 4.1 for this.

Method	Values
Normalization	Yes, No
PCA	10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40
ICA	10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40
LDA	3, 4 / 5–9

Table 3.3: Feature decomposition/preprocessing methods used for all classifiers, alternatively.

Regarding the tools used, for the extraction tool, it was used **Essentia** (Bogdanov et al., 2013), namely the *Freesound extractor* which comes already available in this software package. For feature decomposition, **scikit-learn** (Pedregosa et al., 2011) was used.

3.3 Classifiers

Regarding classifiers it seemed to be difficult to pinpoint which of the most commonly used ones work better. For this reason, it was chosen to do a more thorough evaluation, using different types of classifiers, namely *Support Vector Machines*, *Decision Trees* and *K-Nearest Neighbours*. The software package used for the classification step was, again, **scikit-learn**.

Secondly, two different classification schemes are considered, because, once again, according to the literature review done it was not clear which one exactly work better. These schemes are *flat* and *hierarchical*.

Lastly, regarding the evaluation strategy, a Stratified 10 K-Fold validation is conducted. The stratified part means that for every fold it is guaranteed that it is balanced in terms of number of instances per class.

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion

In this chapter, it is described the two experiments conducted, and presented the corresponding results.

The first one consists of comparing, to the same problem, a content to a context based approach, this work's being the content one and Font et al. (2014)'s the context one. For this experiment in particular, only the first level of the taxonomy is used.

The other one, uses the full taxonomy, therefore classifying instances into something as specific as *Single Note* and *Chord Progression*, to name a few examples. It consists of evaluating which of both classification schemes, *flat classification* or *hierarchical classification* works better.

For all the experiments, it is used three different classifiers: *Support Vector Machines*, *K-Nearest Neighbours* and *Decision Trees*; and two different set of features: *Low-level* and *MFFC+SF* (for more information refer to to Section 3.2).

4.1 Content-based vs. Context-based approach

One of the objectives of this work was to provide a content-based approach to the same problem addressed in Font et al. (2014), which does it using social tags instead. This classification task considers only the *first level* of the taxonomy.

For this evaluation, it was used different classifiers combined with a grid search of several of its parameters to optimize them for the particular classification task and consequently its performance, using the parameters in Table 4.1. For a full description of the parameters please refer to `scikit-learn` documentation¹.

Table 4.2 shows the best performing results for each classifier and each set of features obtained for this experiment, as well as the performance of a random classifier and a summary of Font et al. (2014) results.

Font et al. (2014) uses the tags that have been described by the users in order to predict the class of the first level taxonomy. In this work, it is reported metrics for both SVM and NV (Naive Bayes) classifiers using from one tag to train the classifier

¹<http://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/classes.html>

Variable	Values
<i>SVM</i>	
Penalty (C)	0.1, 1, 2, 5, 10
Kernel coefficient (gamma)	0.1, 1, 10, 100, 1000
<i>KNN</i>	
Number of neighbors	5–12
Weights	distance, uniform
Distance metric	Manhattan, Euclidean
<i>Decision Trees</i>	
Max depth	5-10
Criterion	gini, entropy
AdaBoost (number of estimators)	None, 50, 100

Table 4.1: Grid search parameters used for the content vs. context experiment.

Classifier	Features	Accuracy
Random	-	20%
Font et al. (2014), 1 tag input, SVM and NB	Tags	~70%
Font et al. (2014), 5 tag input, NB	Tags	~95%
SVM C=2, gamma=0, LDA(4)	Low-level	70%
SVM C=1, gamma=0, LDA(4)	MFCC+SF	73%
KNN Manhattan Distance, distance, knn=6, PCA(30)	Low-level	76%
KNN Manhattan Distance, distance, knn=5, ICA(30)	MFCC+SF	78%
Decision Trees AdaBoost(100), gini, 7, LDA(4)	Low-level	82%
Decision Trees AdaBoost(100), gini, 8, LDA(4)	MFCC+SF	83%

Table 4.2: Classification results comparison for the content vs. context experiment.

to up to 5 tags. The results from Font et al. (2014) listed in Table 4.2 are taken from the original paper and not “recomputed” with the same dataset. However, since they are very similar, the results should be comparable, but that more thorough comparison should be carried on to make stronger claims. In any case, and as expected, the more tags the better the prediction as the results showed: $\simeq 70\%$ with one tag and $\simeq 95\%$ for five tags. However, the more tags used, the more “knowledge” about the sound itself has to be known before hand. In sound clip sharing websites, as it is the case of Freesound, it would be great to be able to make tag suggestions during the annotation process, even without the user has described any tag at all. That said, it is fair to consider that any

content-based classifier that has similar performance to a context based one that uses as little as one tag, is already interesting and has possible applications. From that point of view, all of the content based classifiers presented in Table 4.2 achieve this goal.

Another two interesting observations can be made from the results obtained. The first one is that for every classifier a better performance can be achieved using the *MFCC+SF* set of features. The difference is not very big, but is consistent for all classifiers. The conclusion that can be extracted from this observation, is that both the MFCCs and Spectral features used are more representative of the taxonomy used than the other set of features.

Secondly, is that the best scores for every scenario use feature decomposition techniques. In fact, all the scores that were computed without such methods were very much subpar the best results obtained and presented in Table 4.2, most of them under 50%. Also, Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) consecutively achieved good results. Even though that for the K-Nearest Neighbours algorithm that was not the method achieving the best performance, with LDA, the results were both $\simeq 70\%$ for the two set of features, which is still very similar to the best scores obtained with this classifier algorithm, therefore showing evidence of the efficiency of this decomposition technique.

Figure 4.1 shows the confusion matrices for each of the best performing classifiers algorithms, which allows for an analysis of common misclassifications patterns. The very first observation, that can not be really done using the overall accuracy of the 5 classes, is that the class of *Sound Effects* (*FX* in the legend of the plots), is the class consecutively having the worse accuracy. That is intuitively plausible, since this class (along with the *Soundscape* one, which performs two times as the second worse class in the plots in comparison), embraces, by definition, a more diversified set of sounds than the other classes: from sounds of doors slamming, to running water and explosions.

In the context based approach, Font et al. (2014) mentions that, despite not existing very strong patterns regarding the confusion between category pairs, it happens that confusion between the pairs *Instrument-Music*, *Speech-Soundscape* and *Soundscape-Sound Effects* occur more often. To some extent, the same happens in the content-based approach, with the exception of the *Instrument-Music* pair, which has low confusions values for all cases. The hypothesis for explaining this low confusion rate is that users tag these two categories in a not so distinctive way, maybe using similar words for both categories. An example would be instrument names, that is, a user would tag as easily a sound of category *Sample* (e.g. an E open string) or of category *Music* (a A major chord) with the tag *guitar*, ultimately leading to a confusion error in this pair in a context-based approach. With the content based approach, the assumption is that the class is represented by the descriptors, which, in the example given of the E open string and the A major chord, it is known they are very different. On the other side, for the other two pairs mentioned by Font et al. (2014), *Speech-Soundscape* and *Soundscape-Sound Effects*, they are present in the top two highest confusion errors highlighted in red in Figure 4.1, along with also *Speech-Sound Effects*. Font et al. (2014), highlights reasons for this, that we hypothesize to be equally valid for a content based approach. However, the main hypothesis is that in fact the descriptors being used are not enough

(a) SVM (73%)

(b) KNN (78%)

(c) Decision Trees (83%)

Figure 4.1: Comparison of different classifiers confusion matrices for the content vs. context experiment. Highest two confusion errors highlighted in red boxes.

to effectively differentiate these categories, even though they are semantically different. In fact, apart from the *Music-Instrument* pair, which is the one that appears to work consecutively good all the time, all the others pose some kind higher confusion rate than desired. This is promising, since for the experiment of evaluation different classification schemes, the errors in this pair in the first level classification would propagate to the second stage.

4.2 Flat vs. Hierarchical classification scheme

Another of the objectives of this work was to build a classifier for the second level of the taxonomy, while comparing two possible ways of accomplishing that, namely comparing a *flat* classification scheme (as seen in Figure 4.2) to a *hierarchical* one (as seen in Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.2: Classification scheme for the *flat* classifier.

Figure 4.3: Classification scheme for the *hierarchical* classifier.

That said, Table 4.3 shows the results for this experiment comparing classification schemes. In the same manner as in the previous experiment, a grid search is done in order to optimize the classifiers, except for the top classifier of the hierarchical scheme, which optimized configuration is known already. Also, the features used are only *MFCC+SF*, since in the previous experiment, Section 4.1, they consistently performed better.

Classifier	Scheme	Accuracy
Random	-	10%
KNN	Flat	74%
KNN	Hierarchical	75%
SVM	Flat	67%
SVM	Hierarchical	71%
Decision Trees	Flat	57%
Decision Trees	Hierarchical	64%

Table 4.3: *Flat* vs. *Hierarchical* classification scheme results.

Two interesting observations can be made. The first one is that *hierarchical* classification scheme outperforms the *flat* one for every classifier type. According to Babbar et al. (2013), as mentioned in Section 2.5, a flat classification scheme was expected to work better, considering that this work’s taxonomy is well-balanced rather than large-scaled and unbalanced. Furthermore, both Roma et al. (2010) and Burred (2005) works show the hierarchical scheme performed marginally better than a flat approach, which naturally goes against this case.

The second observation is that the biggest improvement is on the Decision Tree classifier (7% points), which is somewhat expected, since this classifier is known to generally perform much better on a reduced number of target classes. In addition, this classifier on the previous experiment, was the best performing one in the previous experiment, which further validates this reasoning.

Finally, it is interesting to observe that the SVM algorithm has similar performance to when evaluating only the first level taxonomy, only having dropped two percentage points, from 73% to 71%. This is probably the reason why they are widely acknowledged as the leading general discriminative approach for machine learning problems in number of domains, audio clip classification included.

Chapter 5

Conclusions and Future Work

In this final chapter, a summary of the conclusions that were possible to come to due to this work are provided. Additionally, because no work is ever really completely finished, it is also described which next steps could be done in order to improve the results and expand it, trying to tackle issues that were not possible to address or further investigate.

5.1 Conclusions

This work consisted of two experiments: a *content* vs. *context* approaches and a *flat* vs. *hierarchical* classification schemes. For the first one, it was possible to conclude that, in first place, the performance values obtained were better than when using few tags in the context based approach, but worse when using more tags. However, the content approach has the advantage of not requiring any “additional knowledge” apart from the signal itself, therefore making it a good choice for something as a first step tag suggestion algorithm. This same experiment also allowed to conclude the MFCC+SF features were better to discriminate between the first level of the taxonomy than the low-level set of features. Also, most accuracy values, when no preprocessing or decomposition technique was used were near random performance, therefore showing evidence that this kind of algorithms are crucial to the task success. Additionally, although that is not reflected in the best performing classifiers for each type of classification algorithm, it was repeatedly observed that very different accuracies would be obtained for the two different set of features, differences as big from 70% using MFCCs+SF to 25% using the low-level ones.

The other experiment allowed to study, in the particular case of this taxonomy, if the *flat* or *hierarchical* classifier would perform better. The results obtained showed that the *hierarchical* classification scheme worked better consistently with all classifiers. This goes somewhat against what the literature review done would expect the author to think, however, at the same time, it still intuitively, makes sense the *hierarchical* performing better, especially considering that the features, apparently are not that optimized as in other literature works. Additionally, the fact that it was obtained high accuracy for the two classes that had sub categories, *Music* and *Sample*, further validates this. These

both show that the *flat vs hierarchical* debate seem to be dependent on the problem.

Overall, this study proposed a system for classifying into the two levels of the taxonomy, with satisfactory results, while also contributing to the sound clip classification field. Furthermore, it also provides the community with a annotated dataset that can easily be used by other researchers.

5.2 Future Work

One of the obvious directions that could be suggested for this work, would be to further expand it. However, despite the results achieved were satisfactory, the author believe there is still space for improvement, before taking that step. This consideration comes in particular, considering the context in which this classifier was developed, namely, Freesound, where there is a lot of focus on the user part. In other words, fully automating every process, it is not really a priority, but more of trying to add value to, naturally to research itself, but also to the Freesound project. That said, and also taking into consideration the natural ambiguity of some sounds as mentioned in Section 3.1, it would be of interest to do a systematic analysis of the errors of the classifiers from the users perspective. That is to say, to evaluate if the errors that the classifiers tend to do are similar (or not) to some human errors too.

Another possible interesting future direction of this work could be to study to which extent incorporating classifiers such as this one (or maybe a improved version) would affect the way users describe their sounds in Freesound, namely if the perceived quality of the descriptions improve and also using other objective measures used in literature, as done in Font and Serra (2012).

Regarding the improvement of the accuracy of the overall classifiers, the author feel that the biggest issue in the current approach is in the feature selection. For this reason, it would be really interesting to further explore other and more automatic feature selection algorithms. To name a few examples, as mentioned in Section 3.2, approaches such as Peeters and Rodet (2002), Livshin et al. (2003) and Roma et al. (2010) would be possibilities to consider.

Appendix A

List of features

A.1 MFCCs and Spectral Features (MFCC+SF)

```
1 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_0
2 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_1
3 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_2
4 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_3
5 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_4
6 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_5
7 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_6
8 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_7
9 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_8
10 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_9
11 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_10
12 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_11
13 lowlevel.mfcc.mean_12
14 lowlevel.mfcc.var_0
15 lowlevel.mfcc.var_1
16 lowlevel.mfcc.var_2
17 lowlevel.mfcc.var_3
18 lowlevel.mfcc.var_4
19 lowlevel.mfcc.var_5
20 lowlevel.mfcc.var_6
21 lowlevel.mfcc.var_7
22 lowlevel.mfcc.var_8
23 lowlevel.mfcc.var_9
24 lowlevel.mfcc.var_10
25 lowlevel.mfcc.var_11
26 lowlevel.mfcc.var_12
27 lowlevel.spectral_centroid.mean
28 lowlevel.spectral_centroid.var
29 lowlevel.spectral_complexity.mean
30 lowlevel.spectral_complexity.var
31 lowlevel.spectral_contrast.mean_0
32 lowlevel.spectral_contrast.mean_1
33 lowlevel.spectral_contrast.mean_2
34 lowlevel.spectral_contrast.mean_3
35 lowlevel.spectral_contrast.mean_4
36 lowlevel.spectral_contrast.mean_5
37 lowlevel.spectral_contrast.var_0
38 lowlevel.spectral_contrast.var_1
39 lowlevel.spectral_contrast.var_2
40 lowlevel.spectral_contrast.var_3
```

```

41 | lowlevel.spectral_contrast.var_4
42 | lowlevel.spectral_contrast.var_5
43 | lowlevel.spectral_crest.mean
44 | lowlevel.spectral_crest.var
45 | lowlevel.spectral_decrease.mean
46 | lowlevel.spectral_decrease.var
47 | lowlevel.spectral_energy.mean
48 | lowlevel.spectral_energy.var
49 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_high.mean
50 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_high.var
51 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_low.mean
52 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_low.var
53 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_middle_high.mean
54 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_middle_high.var
55 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_middle_low.mean
56 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_middle_low.var
57 | lowlevel.spectral_flatness_db.mean
58 | lowlevel.spectral_flatness_db.var
59 | lowlevel.spectral_flux.mean
60 | lowlevel.spectral_flux.var
61 | lowlevel.spectral_kurtosis.mean
62 | lowlevel.spectral_kurtosis.var
63 | lowlevel.spectral_rms.mean
64 | lowlevel.spectral_rms.var
65 | lowlevel.spectral_rolloff.mean
66 | lowlevel.spectral_rolloff.var
67 | lowlevel.spectral_skewness.mean
68 | lowlevel.spectral_skewness.var
69 | lowlevel.spectral_spread.mean
70 | lowlevel.spectral_spread.var
71 | lowlevel.spectral_strongpeak.mean
72 | lowlevel.spectral_strongpeak.var

```

Listing A.1: *MFCC+SF* full list of features

A.2 Low-level

```

1 | lowlevel.barkbands_kurtosis.mean
2 | lowlevel.barkbands_kurtosis.var
3 | lowlevel.barkbands_skewness.mean
4 | lowlevel.barkbands_skewness.var
5 | lowlevel.barkbands_spread.mean
6 | lowlevel.barkbands_spread.var
7 | lowlevel.dissonance.mean
8 | lowlevel.dissonance.var
9 | lowlevel.hfc.mean
10 | lowlevel.hfc.var
11 | lowlevel.pitch.mean
12 | lowlevel.pitch.var
13 | lowlevel.pitch_instantaneous_confidence.mean
14 | lowlevel.pitch_instantaneous_confidence.var
15 | lowlevel.pitch_salience.mean
16 | lowlevel.pitch_salience.var
17 | lowlevel.silence_rate_20dB.mean
18 | lowlevel.silence_rate_20dB.var
19 | lowlevel.silence_rate_30dB.mean
20 | lowlevel.silence_rate_30dB.var
21 | lowlevel.silence_rate_60dB.mean

```

```
22 | lowlevel.silence_rate_60dB.var
23 | lowlevel.spectral_centroid.mean
24 | lowlevel.spectral_centroid.var
25 | lowlevel.spectral_complexity.mean
26 | lowlevel.spectral_complexity.var
27 | lowlevel.spectral_crest.mean
28 | lowlevel.spectral_crest.var
29 | lowlevel.spectral_decrease.mean
30 | lowlevel.spectral_decrease.var
31 | lowlevel.spectral_energy.mean
32 | lowlevel.spectral_energy.var
33 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_high.mean
34 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_high.var
35 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_low.mean
36 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_low.var
37 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_middle_high.mean
38 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_middle_high.var
39 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_middle_low.mean
40 | lowlevel.spectral_energyband_middle_low.var
41 | lowlevel.spectral_flatness_db.mean
42 | lowlevel.spectral_flatness_db.var
43 | lowlevel.spectral_flux.mean
44 | lowlevel.spectral_flux.var
45 | lowlevel.spectral_kurtosis.mean
46 | lowlevel.spectral_kurtosis.var
47 | lowlevel.spectral_rms.mean
48 | lowlevel.spectral_rms.var
49 | lowlevel.spectral_rolloff.mean
50 | lowlevel.spectral_rolloff.var
51 | lowlevel.spectral_skewness.mean
52 | lowlevel.spectral_skewness.var
53 | lowlevel.spectral_spread.mean
54 | lowlevel.spectral_spread.var
55 | lowlevel.spectral_strongpeak.mean
56 | lowlevel.spectral_strongpeak.var
57 | lowlevel.zerocrossingrate.mean
58 | lowlevel.zerocrossingrate.var
```

Listing A.2: *Low-level* full list of features.

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